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SOCIO-ECONOMIC AND HUMANITARIAN ASPECTS RELEVANT TO POST-WAR RENOVATION OF UKRAINE IN EUROPEAN INTEGRATION PERSPECTIVE

Multidimensional aggression of Russian Federation and attempts of occupying Ukrainian territories caused waves of mass migration of population from Eastern and Southern Ukraine to its Western regions or to European Union, where forced refugees have got temporary shelters and favorable conditions for accommodation, also psychological and medical assistance, employment proposals and possibility to continue education into primary, secondary, professional and higher education institutions. Result of Russian military aggression is damaged or totally destroyed objects of critical infrastructure and civic buildings in urban and especially rural areas of Eastern and Southern Ukraine. Analyzing current situation in Ukraine and European Union countries, we have found some coherent tendencies: (1) in general Europe are overcrowded by Ukrainian and Syrian refugees and temporary asylum seekers, that negatively changed economic situation in regional budgets and influenced on live costs; (2) many of Ukrainian citizens wish to return into Ukraine as soon as it will be possible to start its renovation but it will be needed required conditions for their temporary accommodation and staff training for performing strategic tasks or local renovation (especially in rural areas); (3) Ukraine now has deep crisis in humanitarian and educational spheres caused by chaotic reforms, extension of shadow economy sector of agrifood industry, also by the last land law reforms and so-called "optimization" of regional agrotechnical educational institutions networks initiated by group of personally interested governmental officials aspiring to get total control on finances, material assets and lands of national and state educational institutions to redistribute these resources among private stakeholders; (4) essential need on regional and country levels in strategic planning and constructing models of sustainable development (human capital, supply chain management, entrepreneurship, small business, international cooperation etc.); (5) interest of Ukrainian stakeholders (local communities, industry, state entities and educational sector

representatives) in renovation of historical and building new contacts with European and Western partners and potential investors; (6) renovation and rebuilding of ruined and destroyed enterprises and critical infrastructure objects related with food supply chain according to philosophy of circular economy; (7) interest of potential investors and European donors to development in Ukraine transparent legal procedures and guarantees for target investments in Ukrainian agrifood sector to foster global food security.

Figure 1. Strategic civic infrastructure ruining of Ukraine since 24 February, 2022.
(Compiled by author, Garmyk L using Map of ruining, 2022).

Thus, joining efforts of leading Ukrainian regional experts and prominent European experience we can find out valid solutions for listed above complicated and sometimes controversial issues. Studying situation with disproportional development of rural and urban territories in traditional agrarian regions of European countries (mass migration of youth from countryside to big cities, need in qualified specialists for agrifood sector) and popularization of circular economy philosophy, we have found that such results may be actual not for Ukraine or European countries, it also can be used as conceptual framework model for post-war renovation or rebuilding of economically and ecology depressive regions around the world.

Considering nature of required social innovations, today we need instruments that should be effective in identifying, designing and implementing new solutions to social and, indeed, environmental problems. And, in the same time they should be oriented on seeking optimal solutions to increase socially desirable outcomes, such as well-being and health, quality of life, social inclusion, solidarity, citizen participation, environmental quality, and the efficiency of public

services. Social innovation must join together private, public and non-profit actors with citizens to develop innovative solutions aimed on facilitating to economic system renovation [3].

Figure 2. Conceptualization of societal innovative frameworks. (Compiled by authors).

According to priorities posted on web resource recovery.gov.ua, major attention is paid to social inclusion and facilitation to people with special needs, digitalization and anticorruption. The most important role in this will play human capital and responsibility for its recovery, renovation and further development on base of leading universities and their network of vocational schools, as like as it can be done on base of State biotechnological university.

The university was founded in 2021 by joining into one organization four leading agrotechnical universities. But due to administrative falters and managerial crisis in newborn organization, accompanied by deployment of military maneuvers on territory of Kharkiv region, many of leading scholars and scientific-pedagogical staff members have to gone abroad with minimized motivation to came back into Ukraine. Thus, emerging here societal crisis we can solve if involve European partners to conduct diagnostic audit of State Biotechnological University. Using results of this audit after optimization of university top management structure it can being involved to participation into all-Ukrainian programs and measures for the restoration of the country, as well as the development and implementation of policies and measures for the restoration and development of the de-occupied territories of the East and South of Ukraine. Dormitories and university campus buildings today demonstrate readiness to accept and accommodate of temporary replaced persons and repatriates among whom can be people with disabilities, and special educational needs. Nowadays it is possible to develop and implement short-term programs for training or retraining people taking into account the principles of inclusion and European standards and practices. Kharkiv region is ready and has the necessary human capital for the successful implementation of this project. Food security and socio-economic revival of Eastern Ukraine is one of the priorities for Kharkiv region.

References

1. План відновлення України. (n. d.). <https://www.recovery.gov.ua/> Accessed: 4 February, 2023.
2. Map of ruining. (2022). In: Recovery plan for Ukraine [In Ukrainian: Plan vidnovlennya Ukrayiny]. <https://recovery.gov.ua>. Accessed: 4 February, 2023.
3. Juvonen J. et al. (2019). Promoting Social Inclusion in Educational Settings: Challenges and Opportunities. *Educational Psychologist*, 54(4), 250–270. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2019.1655645>